

REVIEW OF IPL TEAMS PERFORMANCE THROUGH MANAGERIAL FACTORS

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Abstract:

The current study was to classify how the managerial factors affect the team identification. The conceptual model of managerial factors affecting team identification proposed that the managerial factors were represented by five primary dimensions: (1) organization, (2) Performance, (3) affiliation, (4) media, and (5) tradition. Among these only two managerial factors Performance and Organization were selected for the study. The participants were volunteered with their interest. To achieve the purpose this study, the data were collected from students (fans) from Bharathiar University (n= 365). Only 328 participants' data were taken for statistical purpose. The IPL team had classified in to five namely Chennai Super Kings (CSK), Mumbai Indian, Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH) with their popularity and past Performance. To test the hypothesis the collected data was analyzed by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) 0.05 level of significance fixed. The result of the study indicates that there was a significant difference between Chennai Super Kings (CSK), Mumbai Indian, Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH).

Introduction:

Overview:

Cricket is believed to be a religion in India and people of all faiths, caste creed and language remain glued to the TV or the radio to watch international level matches. It is also the richest sport in India and top players have star status and earn millions of rupees through game appearance fees and endorsements. The Indian Premier League - IPL is a '20-20' version of Cricket where professional club teams from different cities play about 80 games with a final game deciding the champion. The traditional format is the 'Test' match format with the match of 5 days and two innings. The relatively recent format of one-day '50-50' series has 50 overs bowled by each team. In the 'Twenty20' game each team plays 20 over's. Millions of people around the world watch the games and after the Olympics, FIFA World Cup and Euro Cup, cricket is one of the most watched games. Started in 2008, IPL series and brand was valued at 4.13 billion USD in 2009.

About Cricket:

The game of Cricket in India is a passion that binds people from different religions, political affiliations, languages and economic background. Introduced by the British when they ruled India, the game is played by across the globe by a handful of common wealth nations such as India, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, West Indies, Zimbabwe, Bangladesh, Britain and other new entrants. The number of people who watch and follow cricket in these cricket-playing nations is collectively more than a billion. Millions of people watch matches between rivals such as India and Pakistan and between England and Australia.

About IPL (Indian Premier League):

The Indian Premier League (IPL, officially Vivo Indian Premier League for sponsorship reasons) is a professional Twenty20 cricket league in India contested during April and May of every year by teams representing Indian cities. The league was founded by the Board of Control for Cricket in India (BCCI), however Lalit Modi, the founder and former Commissioner, was the brainchild behind the birth of this league in 2007, which has now become a mammoth, money-spinning cricket venture. Vivo, the Chinese based smart phone multinational company, is serving as the title sponsor since the ninth season of the league.

IPL (Indian Premier League) – the Franchise:

The Indian Cricket League (ICL) was founded in 2007, with funding provided by Zee Entertainment Enterprises. The ICL was not recognised by the Board of Control for Cricket in India (BCCI) or the International Cricket Council (ICC) and the BCCI were not pleased with its committee members joining the ICL executive board. To prevent players from joining the ICL, the BCCI increased the prize money in their own domestic tournaments and also imposed lifetime bans on players joining the ICL, which was considered a rebel league by the board.

On 13 September 2007, the BCCI announced the launch of a franchise based Twenty20 cricket competition called Indian Premier League whose first season was slated to start in April 2008, in a "high-profile ceremony" in New Delhi. BCCI vice-president Lalit Modi, said to be the mastermind behind the idea of IPL, spelled out the details of the tournament including its format, the prize money, franchise revenue

system and squad composition rules. It was also revealed that the IPL would be run by a seven-man governing council composed of former India players and BCCI officials, and that the top two teams of the IPL would qualify for that year's Champions League Twenty20. Modi also clarified that they had been working on the idea for two years and that IPL was not started as a "knee-jerk reaction" to the ICL. The league's format was similar to that of the Premier League of England and the NBA in the United States.

In order to decide the owners for the new league, an auction was held on 24 January 2008 with the total base prices of the franchises costing around \$400 million. At the end of the auction, the winning bidders were announced, as well as the cities the teams would be based in: Bangalore, Chennai, Delhi, Hyderabad, Jaipur, Kolkata, Mohali, and Mumbai. In the end, the franchises were all sold for a total of \$723.59 million. The Indian Cricket League soon folded in 2008.

Currently, with eight teams, each team plays each other twice in a home-and-away round-robin format in the league phase. At the conclusion of the league stage, the top four teams will qualify for the Playoffs. The top two teams from the league phase will play against each other in the first Qualifying match, with the winner going straight to the IPL final and the loser getting another chance to qualify for the IPL final by playing the second Qualifying match. Meanwhile, the third and fourth place teams from league phase play against each other in an eliminator match and the winner from that match will play the loser from the first Qualifying match. The winner of the second Qualifying match will move onto the final to play the winner of the first Qualifying match in the IPL Final match, where the winner will be crowned the Indian Premier League champions.

Literature Review

Trail et. al., (2000) propose a theoretical model for interpreting sport spectators' consumption behavior. They identify six factors that influence future sport spectator consumption behavior: motives, level of identification, expectancies, confirmation or disconfirmation of expectancies, self-esteem responses, and the affective state of the individual. In the model, it appears that level of identification plays a crucial role in future spectator consumptions. Team identification influences an individual's cognitive, affective and behavioral responses to the sports event, and the level of identification has an effect on the individual's expectancies for the event. Expectancies about the quality of the event and its outcome can be either confirmed or disconfirmed.

Heere (2005) proposed three elements to explain why fans are considered as members of an organization. First, fans are able to impact the quality of a product. Researchers have stated that teams win more home games than away games; the support of local fans is recognized as a component of a home advantage.

(Mc Alexander, Schouten, & Koenig, 2002) According to the marketing literature a company can use behavioral rituals, events, and routines to strengthen individuals' identification through sharing experiences.

Some researchers discussed about a new dimension for the Cricketing World. They highlighted the initial phase of IPL and the team formation in which players were assigned to various teams by means of auction. Siddhartha K Rastogi asserted about the final bidding Prices, Cricketing attributes of players and to her relevant information. Sanjeet Singh measured the technical efficiency of various teams participating in Indian Premier League. IPL has emerged as a great success and has been called Billion Dollar Baby. However Coates didn't agree with the fact that professional League games help a community or a city to increase revenue. Shashi Kadapa discussed the very high popularity of Indian Premier League with more than 140 million TV audiences and a brand valuation of more than 4 billion USD. He praised the IPL business model for integrating many complex factors like entertainment, glamour, marketing, pricing and the hard hitting Cricket. Moreover, he conducted a detailed analysis of 10 key issues that threaten the viability of IPL strategy, revenue model and sustainability of IPL. IPL has established a benchmark of Cricket marketing in the whole Cricket World.

IPL is the most fashionable and entertainment Sports League in India. IPL provides a platform where international players from different countries and India's upcoming talent play together. Many researchers have tried their hand in figuring out the different aspects associated with the Indian Premier League. Some tried to highlight its impact on the national economy, some tried to analyse the strategies used in IPL, some others discussed its popularity by means of the viewership involved and its brand valuation, while some others tried to evaluate its impact on the game of Cricket. Though many researchers have tried to discuss outcome of IPL – its impact on youngsters, opportunities created for uncapped players and its contribution towards national economy.

Methodology:

Subjects:

The subjects were all participated of all large, Bharathiar University (Coimbatore). The participants were volunteered in good manner. The researcher was collected almost 329 questionnaires.

Research Instrument:

The main instrument used for data collection was a managerial questionnaire designed by Jin-Long Chen (2007) undertaken for this study which include 64 items.

This method revealed a hundred percent returns of the questionnaire since the 365 copies distributed were retrieved. The researcher was able pick only 328 responses namely 84 responses (26%) Chennai Super Kings (CSK), 70 responses (22%) Mumbai Indian, 64 responses (18%) Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), 57 responses (18%) Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB) and 53 responses (16%) Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH). Among five managerial factors (i.e.,) Performance (Attractiveness), Organization, Affiliation, Media and tradition. The researcher had chosen only one managerial variables for this study.

Table 1: Summary of Mean and One Way Analysis of Anova for the Attractiveness (One of the Managerial Factors)

Mean ± SD					Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	'F'-Ratio
CSK	MI	KKR	RCB	SRH					
6.14	5.3	5.33	5.26	4.96	Between	57.41	4	14.35	18.39*
±0.79	±1.03	±0.85	±0.88	±0.85	Within	252.07	323	0.78	

*Significant at 0.05 level. Heart rate was scored in beats/minute.

(Table value required for significance at .05 levels with df 4 and 323 is 2.39)

The obtained F-ratio among CSK, MI, KKR, RCB and SRH are 18.39 which are greater than the table value of 2.39 with df 4 and 323 at .05 level of significance. It was concluded that there was significant difference among the Chennai Super Kings (CSK), Mumbai Indians (MI), Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB) and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH) on Performance. Since the obtained F-test was significant, the Tukey HSD test was used to find out the paired mean difference and the results have been presented in table 2.

Table 2: Tukey HSD Test for the Differences between Paired Means on Performance (One of the Managerial Factors)

Mean					Mean Differences	Confidence Interval
CSK	MI	KKR	RCB	SRH		
6.14	5.3				0.84*	0.43
6.14		5.33			0.81*	0.43
6.14			5.26		0.88*	0.43
6.14				4.96	1.18*	0.43
	5.3	5.33			0.03	0.43
	5.3		5.26		0.04	0.43
	5.3			4.96	0.34	0.43
		5.33	5.26		0.07	0.43
		5.33		4.96	0.37	0.43
			5.26	4.96	0.3	0.43

* Significant at .05 level.

Table 4 shows that the mean differences on Performance between Chennai Super Kings (CSK) and Mumbai Indians (MI), Chennai Super Kings (CSK) and Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Chennai Super Kings (CSK) and Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), Chennai Super Kings (CSK) and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH) were 0.84, 0.81, 0.88, & 1.18 respectively which were statistically significant at 0.05 level of confidence.

Figure 1: Percentage and Mean Values on Performance Chennai Super Kings (CSK), Mumbai Indians (MI), Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH)

Mean differences on Performance between Mumbai Indians (MI) and Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Mumbai Indians (MI) and Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), Mumbai Indians (MI) and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH), Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR) and Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR) and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH), Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB) and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH) were 0.03, 0.04 0.34, 0.03, 0.37 & 0.30 respectively which were statistically insignificant at 0.05 level of confidence.

The values are greater than the confidence interval value of 0.43, which shows significant difference at 0.05 level of confidence. It may be concluded from the results of the study that the Chennai Super Kings (CSK) had an influenced by one of the managerial factors Performance when compared to Mumbai Indians (MI), Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH).

The percentage and Mean values on Performance of Chennai Super Kings (CSK), Mumbai Indians (MI), Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH).

Conclusion:

The result of the study indicated that there is difference between among Chennai Super Kings (CSK), Mumbai Indians (MI), Kolkata Knight Riders (KKR), Royal Challengers Bangalore (RCB), and Sunrisers Hyderabad (SRH) on Performance.

Recommendations:

- ✓ The current study may imply to academics with modified questionnaire.
- ✓ The current study may recommend combining both academics and Sports.
- ✓ The current study shows the clear picture of managerial factors, thus may recommend in organization and administration.
- ✓ The current study may recommend the small club to adapt this managerial technique in to their developmental factors.
- ✓ The current study gives that clear picture of off screen work of sports mangers.

A Way – to New Research:

- ✓ Future research is encouraged to develop a complete construct regarding service, product, and promotion for team sport then examine if the concepts can explain team identification.
- ✓ To avoid confusion the researcher may add few management scales.
- ✓ The future may go up with some more participants.
- ✓ The future research may evaluate the best team in Pro-Kabaddi tournament in terms of management
- ✓ The future research may add academics and sports with modified questionnaire
- ✓ The future research may give the best view to the amateur about the sports management.

References:

1. Abrams, Ando, and Hinkle (1998). Psychological attachment to the group: cross-cultural differences in organizational identification and subjective norms as predictor of workers' turnover intentions. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 24, 1027-1039.
2. Acton (1990). *Tradition*. Notre Dame, Ind.: University of Notre Dame Press.
3. Adler and Adler (1987). Role conflict and identity salience: college athletics and the academic role. *Social Science Journal*, 24, 443-455.
4. Agnew, and Carron (1994). Crowd effects and the home advantage. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 25, 53-62.
5. Anderson (1987). *Communication research: Issues and methods*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
6. Anderson and Gerbing (1988). Structural equation modeling in practice: a review and recommended two step approach. *Psychological Bulletin*, 103(May), 411-423.
7. Anderson and Stone(1981). Responses of male and female metropolitans to the commercialization of professional sport 1960 to 1975. *International Review of Sport Sociology*, 16(3),5-20.
8. Arnett, German and Hunt, (2003). The identity salience model of relationship marketing success: the case of nonprofit marketing. *Journal of marketing*, 67, 89-105.
9. Ashforth, and Mael (1989). Social identity theory and the organization. *Academy of Management Review*, 14, 1, 20-39.
10. Ashmore, Jussim, Wilder, and Heppen, J. (2001). Toward a social identity framework for intergroup conflict. In R. D. Ashmore, L. Jussi., & D. Wilder (Eds.). *Social identity, intergroup conflict, and conflict reduction* (pp. 213-249). New York: Oxford University press.
11. Babbie (2004). *The practice of social research* (10thed). Belmont, CA: Wadsworth/Thomson Learning.
12. Bagozzi, and Baumgartner (1994). The evaluation of structural equation models and hypothesis testing. In R. P. Bagozzi (Ed.). *Principles of marketing research* (pp.860-422). Oxford, England: Blackwell publishers.
13. Barney (1985). The hailed, the haloed, and the hallowed: Sport heros and their qualities-an analysis and hypothetical model for their commemoration. In N. Muller & J. Ruhl (Eds.), *Sport history* (pp. 88-103). Nierderhausen, Germany: Schors-Verlag.